

Cholic Acid induced *N*-Methylhydantoin Synthesis in Microbial System

SHASHI B. MAHATO^{*a}, IPSITA MAZUMDER^a, PETER LUGER^b and MANUELA WEBER^b

^aIndian Institute of Chemical Biology, 4 Raja S. C. Mullick Road, Jadavpur, Calcuta-700 032

^bInstitut für Kristallographie, Freie Universität Berlin, D-1000 Berlin 33, Germany

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The degradation of creatinine to glycine via *N*-methylhydantoin is well established for microbial systems. However, the microbial route to the formation of creatinine and subsequently *N*-methylhydantoin from glycine and arginine in presence of methionine is unprecedented. This work presents microbial synthesis of *N*-methylhydantoin by *Alcaligenes recti* in nutrient medium containing cholic acid. It has been shown that arginine, glycine and methionine present in the nutrient medium are used as substrates by the enzyme system produced by the microorganisms for the synthesis of the product. The metabolic pathway for the formation of the product appears to be the same as is known for its synthesis in the mammalian liver from the three amino acids. The strategic fermentation experiments reveal that formation of transamidinase responsible for transfer of the amidine group from arginine to glycine to form guanidoacetic acid is induced by cholic acid. Interestingly, *A. recti* is an intestinal microorganism and cholic acid and other bile acids are present in the mammalian liver where creatinine is synthesised. As such, it is probable that here also this acid may have the role of an inducer in the metabolic formation of creatinine, the precursor of *N*-methylhydantoin.

The degradation of creatinine to glycine via *N*-methylhydantoin is well established for a number of microorganisms¹⁻³. However, the microbial route to the formation of creatine and subsequently *N*-methylhydantoin from glycine and arginine in presence of methionine is unprecedented.

The formation of *N*-methylhydantoin during the degradation of creatinine involves the enzyme creatinine deiminase which was first purified and crystallised from *Corynebacterium lilium*⁴. Creatinine is formed from guanidoacetic acid by the action of transmethylase which is AdoMet-dependent. The guanidoacetic acid is obtained from two amino acids, namely, arginine and glycine under the catalysis of transamidinase⁵.

During the course of studies on the microbial modification of cholic acid by a strain of *Alcaligenes recti* in nutrient medium, a significant amount (*vide infra*) of *N*-methylhydantoin was found to accumulate. The formation of this compound is attributed to the amino acids contained in the nutrient medium under the catalysis of

various enzymes at different stages in the presence of cholic acid. We studied the microbiological route to the formation of *N*-methylhydantoin from glycine and arginine in order to develop a working model for understanding the formation of possible intermediates in the creatinine metabolism *in vivo* which is an important physiological phenomenon.

The paper reports the fermentation conditions under which *N*-methylhydantoin was formed, the role of cholic acid as inducer, confirmation of the molecular structure of *N*-methylhydantoin by X-ray crystallography and the significance of its formation. The degradation products of cholic acid formed during fermentation with washed cells have already been reported⁶.

Results and Discussion

The nitrogenous compound, C₄H₆O₂N₂, 114 (M⁺) isolated from the fermentation mixtures indicated its identity with *N*-methylhydantoin from its m.p. and different spectroscopic data, viz.

ir, pmr, cmr and mass spectra. Its unexpected formation during fermentation of cholic acid in nutrient medium evoked much interest and prompted us to confirm its structure by single crystal X-ray analysis. The molecular structure of the compound is shown in SCHAKAL drawing in Fig. 1 which also gives the atom numbering

Fig. 1. SCHAKAL drawing of the molecular structure of *N*-methylhydantoin showing also the used numbering scheme and bond lengths (in Å).

scheme. Except for the hydrogens at C(4) and C(5) the molecule is planar. The average deviation of contributing atoms from a least-squares plane through the five-membered ring is 0.008 Å. The distances of the substituent atoms from this plane are for O(1) : 0.007; for O(3) : 0.043 and C(4) : 0.167 Å.

The ring nitrogen N(2) is donor of a hydrogen bond to the carbonyl oxygen atom O(3) of a second molecule related by an inversion center, [N(2).....O(3)' = 2.809 (5) Å, H(2).....O(3)' = 1.88 (8) Å, symmetry operation for O(3)' = $x, 2-y, 2-z$]. Thus, a pair of hydrogen bonds is generated by this symmetry and two centrosymmetrically related molecules form a dimer in the crystal as shown in Fig. 2.

After confirmation of the formation of *N*-methylhydantoin it might appear at the outset

Fig. 2. Dimerization of *N*-methylhydantoin by a pair of hydrogen bonds via a crystallographic inversion center

that it could be a product of metabolism of cholic acid. However, there is no report on steroid metabolism by microorganisms where a nitrogenous metabolite has been formed and it would be rather far fetched to visualise the metabolic formation of *N*-methylhydantoin from cholic acid. Nevertheless, cholic acid playing the role of an inducer at certain step(s) of *N*-methylhydantoin formation seemed reasonable. Isotope experiments have revealed that creatine is synthesised in the liver of mammalian system from three amino acids⁷. Arginine transfers the amidine group to glycine to form guanidoacetic acid which on irreversible methylation by methionine and subsequent ring closure forms creatinine (Scheme 1). Creatinine is formed in the body exclusively from creatine via creatine phosphate. Minute amounts of creatinine are present in the blood (1 mg/100 ml) and it is excreted in the urine by filtration from the glomeruli. In the present study, the nutrient medium contained the necessary amino acids for the formation of creatinine and it was presumed that *N*-methylhydantoin arises via creatinine synthesised *de novo* from amino acids according to the pathway proposed for the mammalian system. The conclusive evidence for the proposed pathway was provided as follows. When fermentation was carried out in basal medium (e) (vide Experimental) containing the amino acids, arginine, glycine and

 Scheme 1 Postulated pathway of *N*-methylhydantoin formation

L-methionine, the product *N*-methylhydantoin was produced. Moreover, *N*-methylhydantoin could also be obtained when fermentations were conducted in medium (b) wherein creatinine medium (c) containing guanidoacetic acid and L-methionine were used. These experiments demonstrated that arginine, glycine and L-methionine are involved in the formation of *N*-methylhydantoin where guanidoacetic acid and creatinine are intermediates.

On the other hand, the fermentation in medium (b) where creatinine was used as the sole nitrogen source showed a rapid cell growth accompanied by deimination of creatinine. The cell growth was measured in a haemocytometer and diminution of concentration of creatinine was determined in a spectrophotometer. The results are shown in Fig. 3. Since the amount of *N*-methylhydantoin formed was determined as a function of decomposition of creatinine the enzyme activity was expressed as the decline in optical density at 234 nm in comparison to the absorbance of 0.5% standard solution of creatinine. The creatinine depletion curve actually shows the fall in activity of creatinine deiminase with time. The curve also shows that the enzyme is produced

during the logarithmic phase of growth of the organism and actually mirrors the growth curve of the microorganism.

Fig 3 Time course of cultivation of *Alcaligenes recti*. *A. recti* was incubated at 37° on a rotary shaker with shaking at 110 rpm under aerobic conditions either in medium (d) or (e) (●) cell growth was measured in a haemocytometer and (○) creatinine concentration was expressed as optical density at 234 nm showing creatinine deiminase activity

Decomposition of creatinine led to the accumulation of *N*-methylhydantoin which was not metabolised any further as was evident from its quantitative determination by mass spectrometry using the intensity of the molecular ion peak. The results demonstrated that creatinine is used by *A. recti* as nitrogen source and not as a carbon source. It was also observed that yeast extract was not essential in the medium either for the growth of the bacteria or for the formation of *N*-methylhydantoin. Formation of *N*-methylhydantoin was not influenced even when the medium (b) was not supplemented with cholic acid. Consequently, it follows that cholic acid had no role in the transformation of creatinine to *N*-methylhydantoin. In other words, the creatinine deiminase generated by the strain did not require cholic acid as an inducer.

The fermentation experiment carried out in medium (c) in presence or absence of cholic acid and formation of methylhydantoin in both the cases revealed that the transmethylase responsible for the methylation of guanidoacetic acid to yield creatine did not require cholic acid as an inducer. That transmethylase is generated by this microorganism has been demonstrated in the study of metabolism of bile acids⁶.

However, the fermentation in medium (d) in the presence or absence of cholic acid gave different results. *N*-Methylhydantoin was formed when the medium was supplemented with cholic acid but it could not be detected when the medium was devoid of cholic acid. This medium in essence contained only arginine, glycine and inorganic salts. It is here that the transaminase activity is found to occur. Transaminase gets induced only in presence of cholic acid. It has also been found that such induction is not apparent when other members of the bile acid series, e.g. chenodeoxycholic acid, ursodeoxycholic acid, deoxycholic acid etc. are used. The results are summarised in Table 1.

The presence of the putative enzymes involved in the different steps of *N*-methylhydantoin form-

ation was demonstrated by assays for these enzyme activities. Creatinine deiminase activity was measured in terms of fall in creatinine concentration against time in the cell-free preparation of the fermentation in medium (b). Transaminase activity was measured in terms of rise in concentration of ornithine in the cell-free extract of the fermentation in medium (d). The measurement was done from the absorbance at 515 nm at different time intervals and the results are shown in Fig. 4. The curve shows that the enzyme is produced at the initial stage of growth and rises to a maximum at about 8 h of growth and steadily declines thereafter and the level becomes very low after 16 h.

TABLE 1—DIFFERENT CULTURE MEDIA AND FORMATION OF *N*-METHYLHYDANTOIN

Growth medium*	Incubation period h	<i>N</i> -Methylhydantoin isolated (+) / could not be detected (-)
(a)	24	-
(a) + 0.1% cholic acid	24	+
(b)	24	+
(b) + 0.1% cholic acid	24	+
(c)	24	+
(c) + 0.1% cholic acid	24	+
(d)	24	-
(d) + 0.1% cholic acid	24	+
(e)	24	-
(e) + 0.1% cholic acid	24	+

*The cells of *A. recti* were grown in four different culture media : (a) Peptone, 1%; yeast extract, 0.5%; beef extract, 0.5%; NaCl, 0.5% in distilled water, pH 7.0; (b) 1% glycerol, 0.05% MgSO₄.7H₂O; 0.1% KH₂PO₄; 0.2% K₂HPO₄ and 0.5% creatinine, pH 7.0; (c) K₂HPO₄, 0.2%; KH₂PO₄, 0.1%; MgSO₄.7H₂O, 0.05%; (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.05%; guanidoacetic acid, 0.1%; L-methionine 0.1%; glycerol, 1%; pH 7.0; (d) K₂HPO₄, 0.2%; KH₂PO₄, 0.1%; MgSO₄.7H₂O, 0.05%; (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.05%; arginine, 0.2%; glycine, 0.2%; glycerol, 1%; pH 7.0; (e) K₂HPO₄, 0.2%; KH₂PO₄, 0.1%; MgSO₄.7H₂O, 0.05%; (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.05%; arginine, 0.2%; glycine, 0.2%; L-methionine, 0.2%; glycerol, 1%; pH 7.0.

The foregoing evidences demonstrated that the transaminase is produced inducibly by the strain of *A. recti* in presence of cholic acid which yields guanidoacetic acid as an intermediate in the pathway of formation of *N*-methylhydantoin.

It appears that this is the first report for the synthesis of *N*-methylhydantoin from basic

Fig. 4. Measurement of transaminase activity with time. (Δ) Ornithine concentration was expressed as optical density at 515 nm showing transaminase activity.

amino acids in bacterial system. It is very interesting to note that cholic acid and other bile acids are present in the mammalian liver where creatinine is synthesised. As such, it may be proposed that in mammalian liver cholic acid acts as an inducer for the synthesis of creatinine, the immediate precursor of *N*-methylhydantoin.

Experimental

Inorganic salts (all Sarabhai Chemical), peptone, beef extract, yeast extract and agar (all Difco Laboratories, U.S.A.) cholic acid, arginine, glycine, methionine, creatinine, guanidine, methylguanidine, guanidoacetic acid, *N*-methylhydantoin and urea were purchased from (all Sigma Chemical) were used, silica gel for column chromatography and tlc (60 HF₂₅₄ Merck) and organic solvents were supplied by E. Merck.

Growth and fermentation conditions : The enrichment culture technique⁶ was employed for the isolation of the bacterial strain using cholic acid as the sole source of carbon under aerobic conditions. After successive transfers, single colonies of a pure bacterial strain were isolated which was subsequently identified as *Alcaligenes recti* (Registry No. IICB 341). It is being maintained in nutrient agar slants at Culture Collection

Unit of the Steroid and Terpenoid Division of this Institute.

The nutrient medium (a) used for production of *N*-methylhydantoin was the following : (a) peptone, 1%; yeast extract, 0.5%; beef extract, 0.5%; NaCl, 0.5% in distilled water; pH 7.0. Twelve (12) flasks each containing 400 ml of the medium were plugged with cotton wool and sterilised by autoclaving at 121° for 15 min. A total of 5 g of cholic acid in powder form was evenly distributed in twelve flasks. The medium with steroid was then inoculated with a cell suspension obtained from 24 h-old culture maintained on nutrient agar slants. The batch of twelve flasks was incubated on a rotary shaker at 100 rev/min at 37° for 24 h in aerobic condition with shaking. The cells were harvested and exhaustively extracted with CHCl₃. The organic layer was evaporated to dryness and a semi-solid residue obtained. It was analysed by tlc. The same experiment was carried out in medium (a) in the absence of cholic acid under similar conditions.

Formation of *N*-methylhydantoin was tested from creatinine by cultivation in the basal medium (b) which contained creatinine, 0.5%; glycerol, 1%; K₂HPO₄, 0.2%; KH₂PO₄, 0.1%; MgSO₄·7H₂O, 0.05% in distilled water; pH 7.0. The culture broth was analysed by tlc and *N*-methylhydantoin was indicated. The reaction was then carried out in presence of 0.1% cholic acid under shaking for 24 h at 37° and the culture broth analysed as above. The cells on being harvested by centrifugation with two washings with 0.02 *M* potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.5) were suspended in 10 ml of the same buffer and then sonicated at 19 KHz for 3 min at 4–8° in an ultrasonic oscillator. The crude cell-free extract was obtained as the supernatant after centrifugation (14,000 × *g*, 20 min). One ml of each crude cell extract contained about 30–60 mg ml⁻¹ of protein. This was added to 4 ml of the reaction medium which contained 150 mM creatinine and 250 mM potas-

sium phosphate buffer (pH 7.5) followed by reaction at 37°. Samples were withdrawn at appropriate times and analysed spectro photometrically as mentioned under analyses to determine the amount of creatinine consumed.

Creatinine deiminase : The microorganism *A. recti* was cultivated in the production medium (b). The culture broth after growth for 24 h at 37° in a test tube containing 5 ml of the production medium was inoculated into 500 ml of the medium in a 2-L Erlenmeyer flask followed by continuous shaking at 37°. The cells were harvested at the middle to late logarithmic phase and cell-free extracts were obtained as mentioned earlier. Protein was determined according to Biuret method⁸.

One unit of enzyme was defined as the amount catalysing the formation of 1 mM of product or the decomposition of 1 mM of substrate per min under the test conditions.

Reaction with cell-free extracts : Degradation of creatinine was followed with the cell-free extract of the microorganism. The reaction mixture contained 25 mM creatinine, 250 mM potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.5) and cell-free extract (10–30 mg protein) in 5 ml. Samples were withdrawn (0.1 ml) at intervals of 8, 10, 14, 18, 20, 22 and 24 h during the reaction at 37° and analysed to determine the creatinine and *N*-methylhydantoin present in the reaction mixture.

Enzyme assay : The reaction mixture for the estimation of enzyme activity contained 150 mM creatinine, 250 mM potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.5) and crude cell extract in a total volume of 4 ml. The amount of *N*-methylhydantoin formed was determined as a function of decomposition of creatinine.

The presence of *N*-methylhydantoin was tried starting from guanidoacetic acid using medium (c) which contained K₂HPO₄, 0.2%; KH₂PO₄, 0.1%; MgSO₄·7H₂O, 0.05%; (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.05%;

guanido-acetic acid, 0.1%; L-methionine, 0.1%; glycerol, 1% in distilled water. The medium was kept under shaking for 24 h at 37°. The cells were again harvested and extracted with CHCl₃. Tlc analysis of the extract showed the formation of *N*-methylhydantoin. The same experiment was repeated under similar conditions in presence of 0.1% cholic acid and the extract analysed by tlc.

A further confirmatory experiment was carried out using arginine and glycine as the starting materials using medium (d) which contained K₂HPO₄, 0.2%; KH₂PO₄, 0.1%; MgSO₄·7H₂O, 0.05%; (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.05%; arginine, 0.2%; glycine, 0.2%; glycerol, 1%; pH, 7.0. The culture was kept under shaking for 24 h at 37°. The reaction was terminated by harvesting the cells and extracting with CHCl₃ and the extract was subjected to tlc analysis. No hydantoin was indicated. However, the same experiment was repeated in presence of 0.1% cholic acid under similar experimental conditions using the medium (d) and the extract was analysed by tlc. It indicated the formation of *N*-methylhydantoin. The cells were harvested by centrifugation with washing with 0.02 M potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7.5), suspended in 10 ml of the same buffer and then sonicated. The crude cell-free extract was obtained as supernatant as described earlier.

Transamidinase : The microorganism *A. recti* was grown in medium (d) and the cell-free culture was collected as the extracellular enzyme.

Reaction with cell-free extracts : Degradation of guanidoacetic acid was followed with cell free extracts of the microorganism. The reaction mixture contained 0.15 ml of 1 M L-arginine monohydrochloride, 0.25 ml of 0.1 M glycine, 1.0 ml of 1 M potassium phosphate (pH 7.5) respectively, and cell-free extract (10–30 mg protein) in 1.5 ml. After 20 min of incubation at 37°, the reaction was stopped with 2.0 ml of 8.3% trichloroacetic acid (TCA). A zero time blank was always included. Cell-free extracts

were prepared at definite intervals of incubation and the amount of ornithine released was measured colorimetrically.

Enzyme assay : The assay of transaminase was based on the estimation of ornithine by a specific and sensitive colorimetric procedure described by Chinard⁹. The reagent was freshly prepared by dissolving 250 mg of ninhydrin in a mixture of 4.0 ml of 6 *M* H₃PO₄ and 6.0 ml of glacial CH₃COOH by heating to boiling for 10 min. The TCA filtrate (1 ml) was added to glacial acetic acid (1 ml) and the warm reagent (1 ml). The tubes were covered loosely with aluminium caps, heated for 30 min at 100°.

The absorbance was read at 515 nm against the reagent blank in a spectrophotometer. Five standards ranging from 0.05 to 0.6 mM of ornithine in a total volume of 1 ml in each case was prepared along with a reagent blank which contained water instead of ornithine. These tubes were supplemented with 1 ml of a solution which contained the incubation mixture obtained as described under the caption 'Reaction with cell free extracts' and TCA. The same assay procedure was applied to the cell-free extract obtained from cultivation of *A. recti* in medium (e). However, the generation of transaminase was not indicated when examined by spectro-photometer in the 515 nm range.

Fermentation was also carried out in medium (e) comprising of K₂HPO₄, 0.2%; KH₂PO₄, 0.1%; MgSO₄.7H₂O, 0.05%, (NH₄)₂SO₄, 0.05%; arginine, 0.2%; glycine, 0.2%; L-methionine, 0.2%; glycerol, 1% in distilled water, pH 7.0. The reaction was terminated after 24 h of cultivation and the broth was subjected to tlc analysis. *N*-Methylhydantoin was indicated. However, when the reaction was carried out under similar conditions in the same medium (e) along with 0.1% cholic acid, no change was found to occur.

Extraction and isolation of *N*-methylhydantoin : In each case, after 24 h of incubation of

the fermentation mixture was harvested and exhaustively extracted thrice with equal volumes of CHCl₃. The organic layer was washed with distilled water and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. After complete evaporation of the solvent, a semi-solid residue (100 mg) was obtained. Tlc examination of the residue with CHCl₃/MeOH (20 : 5) as the developing solvent revealed the formation of the metabolite. The residue was chromatographed on a column of silica gel. The compound was eluted with ethyl acetate/petroleum ether (3 : 1, v/v). It was further purified by recrystallisation from ethyl acetate (yield, 50 mg). Its purity was also checked by hplc.

Analytical methods : M.ps. were obtained in open capillary tubes in a H₂SO₄ bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 177 spectrometer. Hplc was performed in a Spectra physics SP 8000B apparatus controlled by a microprocessor with a SP 8440 uv/vis variable wavelength detector. The column (25 cm × 4 mm i.d.) was packed with octylsilane chemically bonded to silica gel (10 μl particle). Pmr and cmr spectra were obtained with a JEOL-FT-100 spectrometer at 100 and 25.05 MHz respectively, with tetramethylsilane as an internal standard. Uv spectrum was obtained in a Shimadzu spectrophotometer. Mass spectrum was done in a MS-50 mass spectrometer at an ionisation potential of 70 eV. Cell growth was observed by measuring the number of cells per ml in a haemocytometer, and creatinine depletion was determined by comparison of absorbance at 234 nm in a Shimadzu spectrophotometer.

***N*-Methylhydantoin :** It was crystallised from ethyl acetate as needles, m.p. 156–57° (lit.¹⁰ 157°); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3 000, 1 700, 1 500, 1 100, 900 cm⁻¹; *m/z* 114 (*M*⁺, 100%), 86 (*M*⁺-CO, 13%), 43 (*M*⁺-CO-C₂H₂N, 64%) and 42 (*M*⁺-CO-C₂H₅N-H, 71%); pmr δ (CDCl₃) 3.00 (3H, s, N-CH₃) and 3.96 (2H, s, CH₂); cmr δ (CDCl₃) 171.4 (CO), 52.5 (N-CH₃) and 28.6 (CH₂).

Crystallographic measurements : Suitable, but rather small, single crystals of the compound were obtained from solution in methanol. A prismatic specimen with dimensions $0.18 \times 0.13 \times 0.08$ mm, was selected for the X-ray measurements. From preliminary rotation and Weissenberg photographs the space group was determined to be monoclinic, $P2_1/a$. Precise lattice constants and intensity data of a quadrant ($\pm h, k, l$) were measured on a Stoe four circle diffractometer with Ni-filtered $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation. Orientation matrix and lattice constants were refined from 18 high order reflections. Reflection intensities were recorded by a θ - 2θ -scan technique with variable scan range and variable scan speed. Three standard reflections which were measured every 90 min showed no significant variations during the whole data collection.

Crystal data : $\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$, $M_r = 114.10$, lattice constants (\AA , degrees) $a = 8.087$ (6), $b = 12.16$ (1), $c = 5.595$ (4), $\beta = 105.40$ (6), cell volume (\AA^3) $V = 531$ (1), formula units/cell $Z = 4$, X-ray density (g cm^{-3}) $\rho_x = 1.427$, space group; monoclinic, $P2_1/a$, number of independent reflections : 871, unobserved ($1 < 2\sigma$) 116, linear absorption coefficient μ ($\text{CuK}\alpha$) = 10.04 cm^{-1} , no absorption correction, R -value = 0.069, $R_w = [\Sigma(|F_o| - |F_c|)^2 / \Sigma w F_o^2]^{1/2} = 0.064$.

Structure determination : Phase determination was carried out successfully by direct methods (SHELXS)¹¹. All non-hydrogen atoms of the molecule could be identified unambiguously. Least-square refinements with the corresponding programs of the XTAL¹² system proceeded straightforward. First isotropic, later anisotropic thermal

parameters were assigned to all carbon, nitrogen and oxygen atoms. The hydrogens, which could all be located from difference syntheses, were included with isotropic temperature factors, however only the hydrogens at C(5) were refined. A $1/\sigma^2(F_o)$ weighting scheme was used with (F_o) from counting statistics. Unobserved reflections were included in the refinement only if $|F_c| > |F_o|$. After convergence of all parameters a final R -value of 6.9% was obtained. The maximum and average shift/error ratios at the end of the refinement were 0.71 and 0.06. A final electron density map showed all residual density below 0.39 \AA^{-3} .

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